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ESTOPPEL AND THE ATTITUDE OF THE NIGERIAN COURTS TOWARDS INSTITUTION AND PROOF OF LEGAL ACTIONS BY INSTALLMENTS

By Hassan Umar, Umar Mohammed**, Shamsuddeen Magaji, PhD***, Habib Umar Esq.*****

Abstract

The Law frown at the litigants who will be filing their cases by installment and this is based on the principle of the Law that there must be an end to litigation, if the door is left opened for anyone who had fought and lost a case to produce fresh evidence; there will be no end to litigation. Litigants are always advised to look at all the areas of disputes particularly issues that are relevant to the same subject matter before an action can be instituted. However, some of the rules of court make provision for pre-action counseling to make sure that parties are adequately advised before an action can be filed on their behalf. A party is estopped from litigating on an issue which had been previously litigated and pronounced upon by the court. The attitude of the Nigerian courts is that no party will be allowed to prove his case by installment. This paper seeks to examine estoppel and Res judicata visa vis their applicability in the Nigerian courts and how the courts are dealing with the attitudes of the litigants in the institution and proof of legal actions by installments. On the one hand, the paper will analyse how the issue of installmental institution of actions and proof can be curtailed. The paper will equally examine whether or not parties allowed by law to institute and proof their cases by instalments as well as the conditions for the

successful plea of estoppel and Res judicata. The methodology adopted in doing this research is doctrinal research methodology which essentially is library-based by consulting relevant statutes, decisions of Nigerian courts and other relevant literature. The findings in this research indicate that, the doctrine of estoppel is recognized as part of the Nigerian Law of Evidence. It is recommended that the Evidence Act should be amended to include other types of estoppel covered by the recent decisions of a Nigerian court. There is need to introduce imposition of penalties against parties with the attitude of instituting legal actions and proof by installment on the same subject matter, parties and issues. It is likely that, the penalties if introduced will prevent litigants and or legal practitioners from filing cases based on the doctrine of estoppel and res judicatum to limit unnecessary waste of time of the courts and the respondents.

Keywords: Estoppel, litigants, proof of legal actions, instalments

1.0 INTRODUCTION

One of the recent problems which is overcrowding the cause list of the Nigerian courts and adding to the cost of prosecution and unnecessary waste of time is the issue of institution and proof of legal actions by installment. The position of the Law through the decisions of the Nigerian courts is that there must be an end to litigation and parties to a suit are not expected to prove their respective cases by instalment. The maxim ‘*interest reipublicae ut sit finis litium*’ means that there must be an end to litigation.¹ It is a cardinal principle of administration of justice that a party cannot be allowed to re-open or re-litigate on an issue already determined by the court simply because fresh or new evidence had been obtained. The Law abhors instalmental litigation or multiplicity of litigation over the same cause of action. Sections 169-174 of the Evidence Act 2011 CAP E.14 made provisions in respect of the doctrine of estoppel and the Law has captured some types of estoppel. This paper will discuss the meaning of estoppel and the attitude of the Nigerian courts in respect of instituting or proving actions by instalment. This paper will also discuss some selected types of estoppel in line with the available recent Nigerian cases. The students who will be prepared to be lawyers and judges will find this paper useful in their area of practice.

2.0 ESTOPPEL

Estoppel is a bar that prevents one from asserting a claim or right that contradicts what has been said or done before or what has been legally established as true.² Estoppel also means a bar that prevents the re-litigation of issues³ Estoppel is an affirmative defense alleging good faith reliance on a misleading representation and an injury or detrimental change in position resulting from that reliance⁴. Estoppels are specie of special defenses

* LLB, BL hassanumar262@gmail.com

** LLB, BL, LLM mumar809@yahoo.com

*** LLB, BL, LLM, PhD shamsumagaji@basug.edu.ng

**** LLB, BL haabeebanzeeumar@gmail.com

¹ Dingyadi v. INEC (2011) 10 NWLR (Pt 1255) 34 SC.

² A. Bryan Garner Black's Law Dictionary 8th Ed. (West Publishing Company United State of America) (1990) 589-590.

³ Ibid.

⁴ Ibid.

that are available to the defendant in a suit.⁵ The Evidence Act 2011 CAP E.14 defined Estoppel thus;

“When one position has, either by virtue of an existing court judgment, deed or agreement, or by his declaration, act or omission, intentionally caused or permitted another person to believe a thing to be true and to act upon such belief, neither he nor his representative in interest shall be allowed, in any proceeding between himself and such person or such person’s representative in interest, to deny the truth of that thing.”

2.1 ESTOPPEL BASED ON THE DEFINITIONS OF THE NIGERIAN COURTS

Estoppel is the inhibition to assert a personal benefit or advantage in consequence of a final adjudication of the matter in a court of Law.⁶ According to O Ariwoola JSC “Estoppel is a bar that prevents one from asserting a claim or right that contradicts what has been said or done before or what has been legally established as true.”⁷ The definition as given by O. Ariwoola JSC is similar to the one made by A. Bryan in his book Black Law Dictionary.⁸

“Estoppel is a bar which prevent one from asserting a claim or right that contradicts what one has said or done before or what has been legally established as true. It is also a bar that prevents the re-litigation of issues.”⁹

Estoppel is an admission or something which the law treats as equivalent to an admission of an extremely high or conclusive nature, so high and so conclusive that the party who it affects is not permitted to aver against it or offer evidence to controvert it.¹⁰ In the case of *Adesoji v. Mai-Angwa FUTA* on the meaning and what constitutes estoppel the Supreme Court held thus;

“Estoppel is an affirmative defense barring a party from re-litigating an issue determined against the party in an earlier action, even if the second action differs significantly from the first.”¹¹

⁵ Abubakar v. Tanko 3 NWLR (Pt. 1658) 1 SC

⁶ Menakaya v. Menakaya (2001) 16 NWLR (Pt. 738) 203 SC.

⁷ Tukur v. Umar Uba (2012) 52 (Pt 1) NSCQR 580@ 622.

⁸ A. Bryan Garner (supra).

⁹ Tukur v. Umar Uba (2013) supra.

¹⁰ Ebba v. Ogodo (2000)10 NWLR (Pt. 675) 387 SC.

¹¹ Adesoji v. FUTA (2017) 9 NWLR (Pt. 1570) 211.

The Supreme Court of Nigeria described the nature of estoppel as follows:

“Estoppel is in nature, is a conclusion creating a disability, which precludes a party from contending or proving in any legal proceeding that a fact is otherwise than it has been made to appear by the matter giving rise to that disability”¹²

What can be inferred from the above definitions is that a party cannot be allowed to re-open or re-litigate on issue already determined by the court simply because fresh or new evidence had been obtained. Once an issue had been raised and distinctly determined between the parties to a suit, neither party can be allowed to litigate that issue all over again.

2.2 PARTIES ARE NOT ALLOWED TO PROVE THEIR CASE BY INSTALMENT

It is a cardinal principle of law in the administration of justice that there must be an end to litigation and no party will be allowed by law to prove his case by instalment.¹³ In the recent case of *Akibu v. Race Auto supply Ltd* the court of Appeal of Nigeria held thus;

“There must be an end to litigation. The maxim is interest reipublicate ut sit finis a party or court is not competent to re-litigate the matters or disputes between parties wherein a court of competent jurisdiction has given its judgment”¹⁴

It has become an elementary principle of law that there must be an end to litigation. In the case of *Onyekweli v. INEC* the court of appeal held thus:

“There must be an end to litigation as the society cannot be stable if there is no finality in litigation. It is in the interest of public policy that some decisions of courts are rendered as final because it is in accordance with civilized practice on ground of public policy that there has to be an end to litigation. It is universal judicial practice that is supported by civilized human heritage.”¹⁵

In the unreported case of *Abdulkadir Y. Sulaiman v. The Deputy Sheriff Bauchi State High Court & Ors* in suit Number BA/142/2013 which was affirmed by the Court of Appeal Jos in Appeal No: CA/J/234/2018 also unreported. The plaintiff was unable to prove his claim for

¹² *Access Bank Plc v. N.S.I.F.* (2022) 16 NWLR (Pt. 1855) 143 SC.

¹³ *Akibu v. Race Auto Supply Ltd* (2000) 14 NWLR (Pt. 686) 190 CA.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ *Onyekweli v. INEC* (2009) 6 NWLR (Pt.1136) 19 CA.

damages of demolished property before the lower court. The Court of Appeal, Jos Division affirmed the judgment without making any order as to payment of damages because the plaintiff did not prove his claim at the lower court. However, in a twist the plaintiff filed another action in his bid to prove his claim for special damages in suit No; BA/277/2021. The High court of Bauchi State held that the plaintiff is estopped by record to prove his case for the second time and eventually the action was dismissed. The principle of the law which stipulates that there must be an end to litigation and parties are not allowed to prove their case by instalment always work against the plaintiff.¹⁶

The court of appeal in the case of *Ansa v. Ntuk*¹⁷ held on need for an end to litigation thus:

“There must be an end to litigation and the Law abhors instalmental litigation or multiplicity of litigation over the same cause of action”¹⁸

It is clear from the above decision that the Nigerian courts prohibits the institution of an action or proving same in piece meal or instalment, this is based on the pronouncement of the supreme court of Nigeria that parties as well as the court should minimized cost.¹⁹ The attitudes of the Nigerian courts are that once a case is considered dead; an exceptional presentation must exist for a plaintiff to be allowed to activate a particular case. The Supreme Court of Nigeria held as follows:

“Thus, to activate or resuscitate what is considered a dead case, exceptional presentations have to be available for such procedure”²⁰

The court of appeal in the case of *UBN PLC v. Dappa-Biriye*²¹ held thus:

“Although it is desirable that people should be given the opportunity to litigate in order to avoid tumults, riots and affrays, yet if litigation is not restricted, it might be within the power of wealthy, or the plain mischief maker, to cause nuisance to fellow subjects by spurious litigation which disgruntled subjects might adopt as a hostile attitude to the state who machinery is being so

¹⁶ Ihenacho v. Egbula (2021)14 NWLR (Pt. 1795) 174 SC.

¹⁷ (2009) 9 NWLR (Pt. 1147) 557.

¹⁸ Ibid.

¹⁹ Ihenacho v. Egbula (supra).

²⁰ Ezeonwuka v. Ezeononuju (2018) 15 NWLR (Pt. 1642) 347 SC.

²¹ (2000) 12 NWLR (Pt. 682) 588.

*recklessly invoked against them. It therefore concerns the state that there is an end to law suit.*²²

Also on the same topic the Supreme Court of Nigeria while giving a judgment on the attitudes of counsel and litigants who are engaged on do-or-die attitudes held thus:

“There must be an end to litigation in respect of the same subject matter by the same parties. In the instant case, having protected its interest through the election petition tribunal, the court of appeal up to the supreme court and lost, it was wrong for the court of appeal to allow the 1st Respondent to have a second bite at the cherry to the detriment of the Appellant. A counsel should know and refuse to take a brief in a matter, the outcome of which is clearly intended to re-litigate an existing judgment in rem”²³.

Like in the unreported case of Abdulkadir Y. Sulaiman v. A.A Shafa Limited²⁴ the plaintiff who fought and lost in his bid to prove his claim of special damages on the ground that same has not been proved in suit number BA/277/2021. The learned trial judge held that the plaintiff did not tendered before the court a valuation report for the court to determine whether the plaintiff was entitled to the relief he sought in respect of his claim for special damages for the demolished house. The plaintiff went and obtained new evidence after the case was determined and affirmed on appeal.²⁵ The record of the High Court of Bauchi State in suit number BA/142/2013 was pleaded and argued by all the parties specifically and admitted in evidence. The learned trial judge dismissed the case of the plaintiff who wanted to have a second chance after he obtained new evidence there by stopping the plaintiff from proving his case by instalment. The above cited cases conducted before by the Bauchi State High Court have the same parties; the same subject matter and the same issues. It is clear from the above that the attitude of the Nigerian courts is that no one will be allowed to prove his case by instalment. The court of law being not a football match field is not prepared for a return match.

²² Ibid.

²³ Okorochoa V P.D.P (2014) 7 NWLR (Pt.1406) 213 SC.

²⁴ Suit No. BA/277/2021 (unreported).

²⁵ Abdulkadir Y. Sulaiman v. The Deputy Sheriff Bauchi State High Court & Ors Appeal No. CA/J/234/2018. (unreported)

2.3 ESTOPPEL MUST BE PLEADED

It has become an established principle of law that estoppel must be pleaded for the Nigerian court to give the principle of the law a full consideration.²⁶ Estoppel must be pleaded to avail the party invoking it.²⁷ The general rule is that a plea of estoppel must be specifically pleaded and argued. In the unreported case of *Abdulkadir Y. Sulaiman v. A.A Shafa Limited & 1or* suit number BA/ 277/2021. The plaintiff pleaded and relied on the judgment of the High Court of Bauchi State in suit BA/142/2013 Between *Abdulkadir Y. Sulaiman v. The Deputy Sherriff Bauchi State High Court & Ors.* Moreover, the defendants made reference and pleaded the same judgment and claim that the plaintiff has fought and lost in respect of the same relief. The learned counsel for the plaintiff disagreed with the defendants and maintained that even though reference was made to the judgment in suit No. BA/142/2013, the general rule is that the defence of estoppel must be specifically pleaded; the court disagreed with him. In the case of *Abubakar v. Tanko*,²⁸ an explanation was given in respect the general rule thus;

“Estoppel are species of special defenses that are available to the defendant in a suit. It must be specifically pleaded and argued. The plea of estoppel can be made where an issue of fact has been judicially determined in a final manner between the parties.”

The above pronouncement of the Supreme Court of Nigeria is in respect of the general rule.²⁹ The Supreme Court of Nigeria in the case of *C.B.N v. Aribó*³⁰ made a pronouncement in respect of exception to the general that:

“ It is not necessary to plead it in any particular form so long as the facts constituting estoppel are stated in such a manner that shows the party pleading relies on it as a defense or answer.”³¹

²⁶ *Abubakar v. Tanko* 3 NWLR (Pt. 1658) 1 SC.

²⁷ *Oshodi v. Eyifunmi* (2000)13 NWLR (684) 298.

²⁸ *Ibid.*

²⁹ See also *Oshodi v. Eyifunmi* (supra).

³⁰ (2018) 4 NWLR (Pt. 1608) 130 SC.

³¹ *Ibid.*

The Court of Appeal of Nigeria in the case of *Ogburu v. Ibori*³² took the same position with the Supreme Court thus;

*“A plea of estoppel must be clearly and specifically pleaded, or else it must be so apparent that the court has a duty to consider it.”*³³

*“ ...to this general rule of pleading estoppel, there are two exceptions: estoppel by conduct and estoppel by stand-by do not require to be pleaded specifically. It must however be established evidence and by rule of pleadings, evidence need not pleaded. All that will be required is that the respondent should plead facts...”*³⁴

2.4 NECESSARY CONDITIONS FOR A PLEA OF ESTOPPEL AND RES JUDICATA

The Nigerian courts have over the years set out conditions for the successful plea of estoppel and Res judicata. The following are the conditions;

1. The parties or their privies must be the same³⁵
2. The subject matter must be the same³⁶
3. Issues must be the same in the previous and the present suit.³⁷
4. The court that gave the judgment in the previous suit must be competent.³⁸
5. The must be valid and final subsisting judgment.³⁹

2.5 CIRCUMSTANCES WHEN ESOPPEL WILL NOT BE APPLICABLE

There are certain circumstances when the doctrine of estoppel cannot be applicable and the Nigerian courts have since made their position clear in that regard. The principle of Res Judicata is only available to a defendant and the plaintiff cannot rely on the estoppel or res judicata⁴⁰. The only circumstance where a plaintiff can rely on estoppel is when he is replying to a counter-claim. However, the principle is not applicable on a party who is unaware of the existence of facts he ought to have challenged in the early time. The

³² (2005) 13 NWLR (Pt. 942) 319.

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ M.I.A & Sons L.t.d v. F.H.A (1991) 8 NWLR (Pt. 209) 300-302.

³⁵ Honda Place L.T.D v. Globe Motors L.T.D (2005) 14 NWLR (Pt. 945) 273-291.

³⁶ Ibid.

³⁷ Ibid.

³⁸ Ibid.

³⁹ Ugo v. Ugo (2017) 18 NWLR (Pt. 1597) 218 SC.

⁴⁰ Bassey v. Ekanem (2001) 1 NWLR (Pt. 694) 360 CA.

principle of estoppel does not operate without the knowledge of the other party. The principle only operates when the party to be faulted became aware and did nothing.⁴¹

3.0 ESTOPPEL PER REM JUDICATAM

Estoppel per rem judicatam is a rule of evidence where by a party or his privy is precluded from disputing in any subsequent proceedings, matters which had been adjudicated upon previously by a court of competent jurisdiction between him and his opponent.⁴² The plea of Res judica is used as a shield and not as a sword. However, a successful plea constitute a plea constitutes a bar to any fresh action as between the parties or their privies. Estoppel per rem judicatam is a plea, a bar and as evidence. Where a plea of resjudicata is established; the jurisdiction of the would be ousted.⁴³ This type of estoppel is usually referred to as estoppel by record and is of two kinds thus; Cause of Action Estoppel and Issue Estoppel.⁴⁴

The Nigerian courts have over the years decided many cases which are to the effect that institution of legal actions must not be by instalment and in the same regard parties are not allowed to institute actions already decided by a court of competent jurisdiction and this means that there must be an end to litigation. Moreover, final judgment remained valid and binding on parties until upset on appeal and same can still operate as estoppel. This is premised on the fact that a court properly constituted to decide a case may deliver judgment either correctly or wrongly. Notwithstanding, once a decision is final on the same question and between the same parties it operates as estoppel and the parties are not allowed to re-litigate on the same issue.⁴⁵

3.1 PRINCIPLE GOVERNING APPLICATION OF THE DOCTRINE OF ESTOPPEL PER REM JUDICATAM BASED ON THE DECISIONS OF NIGERIAN COURTS

A plea of per rem judicatam must be mutually enforceable. Thus where privy of estate is set up as the foundation of estoppel per rem judicata, the title relied on to establish such privities must have arisen after the judgment on which res judicata is based or at least after

⁴¹ *Tukur v. Umar Uba* (2012) 52 (Pt 1) NSCQR 580 @ 622.

⁴² *Adeyefa v. Bamagboye* (2014) 11 NWLR (Pt. 1419) 520 SC.

⁴³ *A.G Nasarawa State v. A.G Plateau State* (2012) 50 NSCQ R 337 @ 376.

⁴⁴ *Ogbogu v. Ndiribe* (1992) 6 NWLR (Pt. 245) 40 SC.

⁴⁵ *Abiola & Sons Bottling Company Limited v. Seven-up Bottling Company Limited &Ors* (2012) 52 (pt.3) 1115 SC.

the commencement of the proceedings in the course of which judgment was given.⁴⁶ The plea of estoppel as can be seen in the decisions of the Nigerian courts is of special nature and this is because it operate not only against the parties but also against the court itself since it robs it of its jurisdiction to entertain the same cause of action on the same issues previously determined between the same parties by a court of competent jurisdiction.⁴⁷

4.0 CAUSE OF ACTION ESTOPPEL AND HOW IT OPERATES IN REDUCING MULTIPLE ACTIONS

The cause of action estoppel occurs where the cause of action is merged in the judgment. Therefore, once it appears that the same cause of action was held to lie or not to lie in a final judgment between the same parties and their privies who are litigating in the same capacity and on the same subject matter that is an end to the matter. They are precluded from litigating the same cause of action⁴⁸.

From the above cause of action estoppel can operate to stop multiple action in respect the same subject matter and parties and if cause of action estoppel is successfully raised the cost and time of the litigants in the Nigerian court will be reduced and thereby reducing the number of cases that are on the table of the small number of judges we have in our courts. In the case of *Ikeni v. Efamo*⁴⁹ the Supreme Court of Nigeria while commenting on the application of cause of action estoppel held thus:

“For a cause of action estoppel to arise, the cause of action in the later proceedings must be identical with the cause of action in the earlier proceedings. Where a defense of cause of action estoppel is raised, it connotes that legal rights and obligation of the parties in respect of the subject matter of the action are conclusively or deemed to have been conclusively determined by the earlier action. Cause of action estoppel requires identity not only of the subject matter but also of the parties and issues in the later and earlier proceedings.”⁵⁰

⁴⁶Omiyale v. Macaulay (2009) 7 NWLR (1141) 579.

⁴⁷Timpire Sylva v. INEC (2015) 61 (Pt 2) NSCQR 888 @ 961.

⁴⁸Ibid.

⁴⁹(2001) 10 NWLR (Pt. 720) @ 1 SC.

⁵⁰Ibid.

5.0 ISSUE ESTOPPEL AND HOW IT OPERATES IN REDUCING MULTIPLE ACTIONS

Issue estoppel is an impediment which bars a person from relighting an issue which has been isolated and raised in a particular proceeding and has been finally determined in that proceeding. The rule is that once an issue has been raised and distinctively determined between the parties, then as a general rule neither party can be allowed to fight that issue all over again.⁵¹

The doctrine of issue estoppel is that where an issue has been decided by a court of competent jurisdiction. The court will not allow the same issue to be re-litigated by the same parties. The rule of estoppel is a rule of evidence and the matters which will found an issue estoppel may be of Law or mixed Law and fact but issue estoppel only applies to issues.⁵²

5.1 CONDITIONS FOR THE APPLICATION OF ISSUE ESTOPPEL

Three elements must be established for a plea of issue estoppel to apply. These are:

- (a) The same question must have been decided in both suits;
- (b) The judicial decision relied upon to create the issue estoppel must be final and,
- (c) The parties to the judicial decision or their privies must be the same in both proceedings.

In the case of *Esuwoye v. Bosere*⁵³ in this case, the parties in both appeals were the same but the decision relied upon to invoke issue estoppel was not a final determination thereby rendering the second element not satisfied. Also, the issues involved were not the same. The three elements required for the application of the principles of issue estoppel must be present side by side in the case and the absence of any of the elements render the principle inapplicable.⁵⁴

In the case of *Okukuje v. Akwido*⁵⁵ the supreme court of Nigeria while commenting on the relevant conditions for the application of Issue estoppel held thus;

“Issue estoppel may still arise where a plea of res judicata could not be established because the causes of action are not the same. The conditions for

⁵¹ Bamegbegbin v. Oriare (2009) 13 NWLR (Pt. 1158) 370 SC.

⁵² APC v. PDP (2015) 62 (Pt 1) NSCQR 1 @ 138 SC.

⁵³ Esuwoye v. Bosere (2017) 1 NWLR (Pt. 1546) @ 257 SC.

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ (2001) 3 NWLR (P.t 700) 261 SC.

the application of the doctrine are that: (a) the same question was decided in both proceedings; (b) the judicial decision said to create the estoppel is final; and c. the parties to the judicial decision or their privies were the same as the parties or their privies to the proceedings in which the estoppel is raised. In the instant case, the parties or their privies the issues and subject matter are not the same in the previous case as in the present case. Issue estoppel does not therefore apply.”⁵⁶

The attitudes of the Nigerian courts on this topic is clear in many judicial decisions and what a party need to prove in issue estoppel is that a party will not have to prove the sameness of the subject matter the way and to the same degree he is required to do when relying on estoppel per rem judicatam as a cause of action estoppel.⁵⁷ However, where a party has several issues in respect of the same subject matter he is supposed to put all the issues in one basket and in one single case. A party will not be allowed to be taking the issues one by one and be taking them to different court and there by doing his case in piece meal or by instalment.⁵⁸

6.0 DISTINCTION BETWEEN ESTOPEL PER REM JUDICATAM AND ISSUE ESTOPPEL

The distinction between a plea of estoppel per rem judicatam and issue estoppel is that, in the former the party pleading it must prove that the res, the claim and the parties are the same. In the later, a party pleading issue estoppel need not prove that the parties, the claim and the parties are the same.⁵⁹ Therefore, even when plea of estoppel per rem judicatam is not available to plaintiff or claimant in a case, the plea of issue estoppel can be brought by either party.⁶⁰ This type of estoppel is also referred to as estoppel by record.⁶¹

7.0 ESTOPPEL BY CONDUCT

The doctrine of estoppel by conduct is a common Law principle recognized by the Nigerian Law of evidence. Estoppel by conduct is a bar that prevents a person from a contract that

⁵⁶ Ibid.

⁵⁷ Ekpo v. Ito (1991) 2 NWLR (Pt. 171) 108 CA.

⁵⁸ Abana v. Obi (supra).

⁵⁹ Okungbowa v. Gov. Edo state (2015) 10 NWLR (Pt. 1467) 257 CA.

⁶⁰ Ibid.

⁶¹ Umeche, Chinedum I. "Customary arbitration and the plea of estoppel under Nigerian law." *Commonwealth Law Bulletin* 35, no. 2 (2009): 291-297.

the person has entered in to.⁶² The term estoppel by conduct is also referred to as estoppel by standing- by and they are used interchangeably. Other types of estoppel includes estoppel by deed; estoppel by representation.⁶³

7.1 OPERATION OF DOCTRINE OF ESTOPPEL BY CONDUCT AND THE ATITUDE OF NIGERIAN COURTS

By the rule of Estoppel by conduct, where one by his word or conduct willfully causes another to believe the existence of certain state of things and induces him to act on that belief so as to alter his own previous position, the former is precluded from averring against the later a different state of things as existing at the same time.⁶⁴ In this regard, an arbitration award can validly constitute a ground for an estoppel.⁶⁵

7.2 DISTINCTION BETWEEN ESTOPPEL BY CONDUCT AND ESTOPPEL PER REM JUDICATAM

While estoppel by conduct or estoppel by standing- by and estoppel per rem judicatam can arise from the same set of circumstances, they are however two distinct defenses. Res judicata arises as a matter of record, whilst estoppel by standing-by is an equitable doctrine and is essentially a question of fact.⁶⁶ Looking at the above and the principle of Law regarding estoppel, the effect of estoppel by conduct is that it will prevent a person from insisting on his legal right or will lead to suspension of those rights and this will help in reducing multiple actions in our courts.

8.0 ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS IN RESPECT OF ESTOPPEL AND THE ATITUDE OF THE NIGERIAN COURTS TOWARDS INSTITUTION AND PROOF OF LEGAL ACTIONS BY INSTALMENTS

The Finding of this research is centered on the attitude of litigants and lawyers who are overcrowding the cause list of our courts with multiple actions just because fresh evidence was obtained after the conclusion of matters on merit between the same parties,

⁶² A.G Rivers State v. A.G Akwa Ibom State (2011) 8 NWLR (Pt.1248) 31.

⁶³ Ogbonnaya, John O., and Chinyere Constance Ogah. "Estoppel, A Big House with Many Rooms: An Appraisal." (2013).

⁶⁴ Nsirim v. NSirim (2002) 3 NWLR (Pt. 755) 697.

⁶⁵ Frank-Igwe, Uzo, and Grace C. Okara. "The Legality of Resolving Land Disputes through Customary Arbitration in Nigeria." *Journal of Private and Property Law* 18, no. 1 (2022).

⁶⁶ Nwakonobi v. Udeorah (2013) 7 NWLR (Pt. 1354) 499 SC.

issues and subject matter.⁶⁷ This attitude is consuming the precious time of the courts and the litigants and at the same time, litigants are being subjected to unnecessary economic loss.

The Bauchi State High courts civil Rules 2022 provided some level of sanity in the system by providing a rule for pre-action counseling before an action can be instituted. The rule provided by the rules of courts are not enough since other measures including the amendment of the Evidence Act 2011 should be made to ensure that there are strong penalties for parties who are interested in filing and proving their cases by instalments instead of merging all the issues in respect of the same subject matter.

The doctrine of Estoppel and Res judicata is a principle of litigation that ensures the finality of disputes in order to protect parties from being vexed with the same matter twice. Estoppel is based on the principle of equity and good conscience, the object of which is to prevent fraud and ensure justice between the parties by promoting transparency and good faith. The public interest aspect is the prevention of any legal uncertainty that might arise from re-litigation and the prevention of waste of time and resources.

9.0 CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATION

This research has discussed Estoppel and how the principle of the law and the attitude of the Nigerian courts in reducing the number of cases in our courts that ought to be heard by a single judge and in a single case there by preventing the litigants from filing their respective cases in piece meal or by instalment. The general principle of law and practice in relation to estoppel and the exception to the general rule were also discussed.

In relation to the same topic, the paper has discussed some selected types of estoppel and Res judicata. The selected types of estoppel and Res judicata discussed in light with the Nigerian Case Laws are the most common types of estoppel one can see in our courts. References were made to recent Nigerian case laws particularly on how the cases helped litigants in reducing their cost, waste of time and fraud.

The Evidence Act 2011 CAP E. 14 made provisions in relation to the doctrine of estoppel and this include the definition and some types of estoppel but other types of estoppel which are

⁶⁷ Suit No. BA/277/2021 (unreported)

relevant to this paper have not been captured by the provision of the Evidence Act.⁶⁸ The Act recognized the doctrine of estoppel as being part of the Nigerian Law of Evidence.

It is recommended that the Evidence Act 2011 should be amended to include other types of estoppel covered by recent Nigerian case laws and penalties should be provided for parties with attitude of institution of legal actions and proof by instalment which has to do with the same subject matter, parties and issues. The penalties if provided will prevent citizens from unnecessary waste of time and resources and the cause list of our courts will not be over crowded. However, if the evidence Act 2011 is amended to include penalty for institution of legal action by instalment, the principle of equity and good conscience will be ensured. The amendment will prevent fraud and ensure justice between the parties by promoting transparency and good faith.

⁶⁸ Sections 169-174 of the Evidence Act 2011.